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**PEDAGOGICAL ATTITUDES OF CENTRAL ASIAN ENCYCLOPEDIA
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Annotation: The works of scientists of the Eastern Renaissance have an incomparable place in the formation of social pedagogical ideas and theories. The essence of their activity lies in the fact that the previously existing methods of socialization of that period were collected on the basis of a scientifically based system. the nature of the activity of advanced scientists - preoccupation with science - had an impact on the content of social pedagogical views.

Key words: Pedagogy, science, education, manners, intellectual, psychological characteristics.

To restore the fame of the geniuses of pedagogical thinking of the past. the implementation of their ideas is becoming clear to everyone today. From time immemorial, our fathers and grandfathers paid special attention to raising the young generation to become perfect people with imagination and faith. Our great scholars have taught that humility is the most beautiful human quality, it is defined by human culture, humanity, and courage. The humility of a person is first of all manifested in his cocktail, the air of a humble person is lust, pride. there will be no arrogance, he will be polite - moral, loving - compassionate, in his work. he is firm in his word. Uzbek culture, such as oriental national education, has had its influence on social and political processes in every historical period and stage. In the past, our fathers and grandfathers, our great scholars, and the great enlightened ones saw happiness in freedom and freedom. Abu Nasr Farobiv, Imam A1 - Bukhari, Mahmud Koshghari, Najmuddin Kubro, Abu Raikhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, az-Zamashkhari, Yusuf Khas Hajib, who created a great revolution in the development of science, science and culture in his time. Ahmad Yassavi and others surprised the whole world with their inventions and ideas.

The works of the great scientist Al-Khorazmi (783-850) have a bright didactic character. He emphasized that through the question-answer method, knowledge is mastered, in this process, a person is introduced to relationships with others, and becomes an activist of the society.

Scientists such as Al-Khorazmi-Farabi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Ulugbek understood the idea of focusing the developing, nurturing and educational influence on the growing generation and applied it in their scientific and pedagogical activities.

This was manifested primarily in the fact that they believed that the purpose of education is to prepare for life, acquire moral norms and rules, professional skills and deep knowledge.

The great encyclopedist Abu Raykhan Beruni (973-1050) developed scientific methods used in the educational process. He also classified the principles of education. The social orientation of his pedagogical views is expressed in the fact that he understands morality as an expression of social characteristics and emotions. The scientist's ideas about the importance of science and work in education, personality formation and practical life in society have remained important until now.

The great encyclopedic scientist Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037) left a great scientific heritage covering all fields of knowledge of his time. All his works contain pedagogical views. We consider his ideas about knowledge, will and goal-seeking in the process of human development, the influence of the environment, moral and work education, the art of communication, and the education of children in a team to be important.

Farabi, Ibn Sina, Beruni expressed the same opinion on the problems of education and highlighted the task of education, which allows a person to effectively use his mental, physical, moral, aesthetic and labor skills to serve society productively. In order to implement the developmental task of education, they advised to use the following didactic principles:

- gradual complexity of concepts;
- connect practice with experience;
- ability to accept;
- demonstrativeness.

According to Ibn Sina, socialization skills are best formed in the form of team teaching. For this, it must be based on the following:

1. Organization of exchange of experience, knowledge, spiritual and moral values among learners, teachers and students.
2. Using the element of competition.
3. To develop the student's social and moral characteristics - interaction, mutual understanding, mutual help, and a sense of friendship.

The socio-pedagogical orientation of the pedagogical views and activities of the great scientists is reflected in their interpretation of the purpose of education, which is first of all comprehensive preparation for life. They considered kindness, helping loved ones, pride, conscience, goodwill, and patience to be the most important qualities that ensure a person's place in society. Paying great

attention to all-round intellectual and work preparation of students, Farabi and Ibn Sina considered activity, independent initiative, aspiration, curiosity, and creative ability as the most important factors of young people's "entry" into society.

Allocating a leading place to the teacher in social education, Farabi compares his activity to the activity of a ruler, on whom the future of society depends. Farabi, like Ibn Sina, pointed out that pedagogues should pay attention to students' application of knowledge to life. Encyclopaedists paid great attention to the personal example and served as an example of aspiration and achievement of a high social status. Farabi was extremely hardworking, strong-willed, humble, simple and always eager to help. Farabi's thoughts about the importance of choosing a profession and the method of education that matches the individual psychological and mental characteristics of students are still of great importance.

The understanding of the social role of upbringing and education by Central Asian scientists was shown in the fact that they paid attention to the microfactors of socialization - the environment, the family, the group of students and embodied the actions of parents, pedagogues and students. Thus, the scholars of the Middle Ages left a great pedagogical legacy with a social-pedagogical orientation. Their scientific pedagogical works are an important source for the development of modern social pedagogic science.

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